

Comparative evaluation of Root canal filling removal ability of Novel Rotary files and Conventional Hand H files from Root Canal treated teeth by using stereomicroscope – An Invitro Study

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ABSTRACT-

AIM: The aim of the study was to evaluate and compare the efficacy of Neo-endo, Retreat retreatment file system, Protaper universal retreatment files and H-files for removing gutta-percha from Root canal treated tooth.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Forty extracted single-rooted human teeth with a single canal were opted. The shaping of the root canals were done with rotary files, and later obturated. The samples were grouped based on the file system chosen for removing the obturating material: Group I(n=10)-H-files; Group II (n=10)-Neo-endo retreatment files; Group III(n=10)-ProTaper Universal Retreatment files. Group IV(n=10)- Retreat retreatment files. After retreatment, the roots were grooved in a buccolingual direction and split into two halves using a diamond disc. The quantity of remaining gutta-percha still present after the retreatment procedure were assessed under a stereomicroscope.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS: The data was analysed using one way Anova Test and Post Hoc Tukey Test was used for intergroup comparison

RESULTS - ProTaper Universal retreatment files showed less residual gutta-percha in the root canal compared to NeoEndo, H-files, and Retreat retreatment files.

CONCLUSION- The ProTaper Universal retreatment files proved to be the most effective in removing gutta-percha from the root canal.

Keywords – Retreatment, ProTaper Universal Retreatment System, Neo endo retreatment file, stereomicroscope, Hedstrom files

INTRODUCTION

Although root canal therapy demonstrates a high success rate, it does not always yield the expected clinical outcome and instances of treatment failure may still be observed.¹

RCT can fail due to various reasons, such as:

Anatomical complexities: Unusual root canal structures can make complete cleaning challenging, leading to residual infection.

Technical errors: Mistakes during the procedure, like incomplete debridement or poor obturation, can allow microorganisms to persist and cause reinfection.²

When RCT fails, endodontic retreatment may be necessary. This can be performed either surgically or non-surgically or extraction depending on the specific circumstances of the case.² Retreatment is generally preferred as it is most conservative management for failed endodontic therapy³

The primary objective of nonsurgical retreatment is to remove the previous root canal filling material, regain apical access and facilitate effective cleaning, shaping and disinfection of the canal.⁴ Entrapped tissue or microbes beneath residual gutta percha/sealer can cause periapical inflammation with *Efaecalis* being the most frequent species in root canal treated teeth.⁵

Various methods are used to remove root canal filling material including hand files, NiTi rotary instruments, Gates Glidden burs, heat carrier, ultrasonic devices, lasers and solvents like chloroform, eucalyptol, xylene, orange oil.⁶ With the use of Hand files the removal of gutta percha is difficult and time consuming regardless of solvent use.⁶ Rotary NiTi instruments are effective and safe for removing root canal filling materials offering efficient cleaning, preservation of canal shape and faster preparation compared to hand instruments.^{1,6}

The aim of present study was to compare the efficacy of three rotary file systems, i.e Neo Endo Retreatment files, ProTaper Universal Retreatment (PTUR) files and Retreat Retreatment files with that of manual H-files in removing gutta-percha and sealer from the root canals

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Forty non carious mandibular premolar teeth, each with single canal and fully developed apices were selected and cleaned of calculus and debris with ultrasonics. Preoperative radiographs were obtained in both mesiodistal and buccolingual directions. Teeth were decoronated using a disc to achieve a standardized size of 10 mm of root.

Access opening were prepared in all specimen. A 10 No. K-file was inserted until seen at the apical foramen and working length was established by subtracting 1 mm from this measurement. All instrumentation was carried by a single operator. The canals were instrumented using NeoEndo rotary files upto size 25 with a 6% taper. During canal preparation, 17% EDTA was used to facilitate chelation. After each instrument the canals were irrigated with 2mL of 3% sodium hypochlorite to ensure effective cleaning. For the final irrigation, a sequential rinse was performed using 5mL of 17% EDTA followed by 5mL of sterile saline

The canals were filled using cold lateral compaction with gutta percha (Diadent) cones combined with AH Plus sealer (Dentsply DeTrey, Konstanz, Germany). Excess gutta percha was removed with heated plugger and subsequently compacted using cold plugger for optimal adaptation. Radiographs were taken in both mesiodistal and buccolingual views to assess the quality of filling. Following obturation, the root orifices were sealed with Cavit-G (3M ESPE, Germany) and stored at 37°C in 100% humidity for 2 weeks to allow sealer to fully set.

The prepared samples were randomly allocated into four Groups with 10 teeth in each group. Retreatment procedure was carried out without the use of solvent.

Group 1 H files

Gutta-percha (GP) removal was carried out using standardized assorted H-files up to size 40 (Mani). H-files numbered 40, 35, 30, 25, and 20 were used sequentially to remove GP and sealer until the approximate working length was reached. The files were operated with a quarter-turn, push-pull, and circumferential filing motion

Group II – Neo Endo Retreatment files

According to the manufacturer's instructions, Neo-Endo retreatment files (Orikam Healthcare, India) were used sequentially. Gutta-percha was removed from the coronal third using the N1 file (30/09), from the middle third with the N2 file (25/08), and from the apical third with the N3 file (20/07), applying slight apical pressure at a constant speed of 350 rpm.

Group III : ProTaper Universal Retreatment (PTUR) files (Dentsply Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) It consists of D1, D2, and D3 files that were utilized sequentially in the brushing motion and crown down method at 500 revolutions per minute.

Group IV : Retreat Retreatment files

RM -0.04 Manual SS File Allows the centring and alignment of the next instrument

RE Endoflare 0.12 Rotary NiTi File Apical pressure control stop as soon as instrument requires force to penetrate

Retreat- 0.06 Rotary NiTi File Canal penetration through repeated limited pushing actions in apical direction

Throughout the retreatment after each file change the canals were irrigated with 2mL of 3% sodium hypochlorite and debris adhering to the instruments were routinely removed. Retreatment was completed once the working length was attained and no more gutta percha remnants were visible on the files.

Evaluation of residual Gutta Percha

The roots were grooved buccolingually on both the buccal and lingual surfaces using a diamond disc and then split into two halves. Each segment was examined under a stereomicroscope at 10x magnification, and images were captured using a digital camera.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All the data was entered in Microsoft excel sheet 2009. Descriptive statistics was explored in terms of mean and standard deviation (SD). Intergroup comparison was carried out through ANOVA followed by post hoc tukeys test. All the statistical analysis was carried out through SPSS version 25.0.

RESULT

Table 1: Mean residual obturating material in Group I, II, III and IV

Mean residual obturating material			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Group I (H file)	10	2.20	1.16
Group II (Neo endo)	10	2.0	0.89
Group III (Densply)	10	1.2	0.4
Group IV (Retreat R file)	10	1.8	0.74

Mean overall debris removal of Group I was 2.20 ± 1.16 , in Group II was 2.0 ± 0.89 . In Group III and IV the overall debris removal was 1.20 ± 0.40 and 1.80 ± 0.74 respectively.

ANOVA for between group comparison for residual obturation material showed

statistically significant difference in debris removal between Group I, II, III, IV respectively ($p < 0.05^*$)

Figure1 : showing mean residual obturating material

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	p value	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Group I	Group II	0.2	0.654	-.1907	.0657
	Group III	0.4	<0.05*	.1588	.4152
	Group IV	1.0*	<0.05*	.1580	.4145
Group II	Group I	-0.2	.578	-.0657	.1907
	Group III	0.2	.90	.2213	.4777
	Group IV	0.8	<0.05*	.2205	.4770
Group III	Group I	-1.0*	<0.05*	-.4145	-.1580
	Group II	-0.8*	<0.05*	-.4770	-.2205
	Group IV	-0.6*	<0.05*	-.1275	.1290
Group IV	Group I	-0.4*	<0.05*	-.4152	-.1588
	Group II	-0.2	1.23	-.4777	-.2213
	Group III	0.6	<0.05*	-.1290	.1275

The mean difference is significant at the <0.05 level

Table 3: Pairwise comparison for mean mean residual obturating material between Group I, II, III and IV

Pairwise comparisons using Tukey's post hoc test revealed a statistically significant difference when Group I was compared with Groups III and IV ($p < 0.05$). A statistically significant difference in the overall mean residual obturating material was also observed when Group III was compared with Groups I, II, and IV, and when Group II was compared with Group IV ($p < 0.05$). No statistically significant difference was noted between Groups I and II, Groups I and III, or between Groups II and III with respect to debris removal efficacy ($p > 0.05$).

Group III (PTUR) demonstrated the lowest percentage of remaining root canal filling material among all groups, with a statistically significant difference when compared to Group II (Neo Endo retreatment files) and a highly significant difference when compared to Group IV (Retreat retreatment files) ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, Group I (H-files) exhibited the highest percentage of residual root canal filling material.

Figure 2: The analysis of the remaining gutta-percha/sealer after retreatment in coronal, middle, and apical thirds of the root canal in groups I (H-files), II (Neo-endo files), III(PTUR files) and IV(Retreat Retreatment file)

DISCUSSION

In recent years, progress in endodontic techniques and materials has positioned nonsurgical endodontic retreatment as the preferred management option for failed cases, primarily due to its minimally invasive nature when compared with surgical approaches. In 1986, the late Dr. Herbert Schilder introduced the term “*retreatodontics*” and emphasized that the future of endodontics rests in the retreatment of failed endodontic cases.⁵

Numerous studies have investigated different methods for the removal of root canal filling materials, including the use of hand files such as H-files, rotary instrumentation with or without heat or solvents, and ultrasonic techniques.^{2,4,5,7,8} Horvath et al. (2009) reported that gutta-percha removal without solvents produced cleaner dentinal tubules than solvent-assisted techniques, as solvents promoted residual material penetration into the tubules.⁹ Based on these considerations, solvent use was not used in this study.⁹

One of the most challenging factors to standardize is the inherent anatomical diversity of human teeth, as differences in root canal morphology significantly affect the alterations produced during canal preparation and, consequently, during retreatment procedures.¹⁰ Single-rooted premolars were chosen to minimize variability and procedural complications during canal preparation.¹⁰ To minimize variability, only single-rooted premolars with straight canals were selected, and a standardized root canal filling length i.e 10mm was maintained to reduce procedural complications during canal preparation.

Gutta-percha combined with a sealer is the most widely used obturation system. AH Plus sealer exhibits favorable mechanical properties, adequate radiopacity, long shelf life, and minimal polymerization shrinkage and solubility; therefore, it was selected for use in the present study.¹¹

Various methods have been employed to assess the effectiveness of root canal filling removal, including radiography, digital imaging, canal clearing, CBCT, and sectioning followed by stereomicroscopic examination. Clearing techniques can affect the measurement of residual filling material, while radiography offers only two-dimensional representations of three-dimensional structures and may involve image magnification.¹² As reported by Takahashi et al. vertical splitting followed by stereomicroscopic examination is regarded as a reliable and practical evaluation method, as it is simple to perform and provides advantages over other assessment techniques.¹³ In the present study, the samples were studied under stereomicroscope under 10X magnification.

Traditionally, H-files have been widely used for the removal of root canal obturation materials. Their positive rake angle allows efficient engagement and removal of gutta-percha during withdrawal strokes, providing controlled cutting and minimizing canal wall damage. Additionally, H-files can adapt to canal irregularities, making them suitable for both straight and mildly curved canals during retreatment procedures.¹² NiTi rotary files offer superior flexibility and torsional resistance compared to stainless steel, making them ideal for shaping complex canals. Advanced designs with non-cutting tips, varied cross-sections, and tapers improve safety, reduce preparation time, and maintain canal morphology without zipping or ledging. During retreatment, the frictional heat generated by NiTi rotary files softens gutta-percha, facilitating its easier penetration and removal^{12,14} Therefore, this study aimed to compare the effectiveness of manual Hedstrom files with three rotary retreatment systems, ProTaper Universal Retreatment ,

Neo endo retreatment files and Retreat Retreatment file, in removing gutta-percha from root canals during endodontic retreatment.

The present study demonstrated that the least amount of residual root canal filling material was observed in the PTUR file group (Group III), followed by the Neo Endo file group (Group II) and the Retreat retreatment file group (Group IV), while the maximum amount of remaining filling material was found in the H-file group (Group I).

The effective performance of ProTaper Universal retreatment files in straight root canals, as reported by Gu et al. (2008), was linked to the progressive tapers and active cutting efficiency, which enhance penetration into the filling material and facilitate its removal from the canal walls specific length design of the D1, D2, and D3 files. These features are thought to allow the instruments to remove both gutta-percha and the superficial dentin layer during retreatment.^{15,16}

The groups retreated using Neo Endo retreatment files exhibited a higher percentage of residual root canal filling material compared to those treated with PTUR files, with the difference between Group II and Group III being statistically significant. The reduced amount of remaining filling material observed with PTUR may be attributed to its convex triangular cross-section, which provides a larger internal area compared to the Neo Endo system.

NeoEndo retreatment files feature an active cutting tip and a parallelogram cross-section, which restricts dentin contact to one or two points at any given level. This design minimizes file binding and the screwing-in effect, thereby enhancing both the safety and cutting efficiency of the instrument^{17,18}

The Micro Mega Retreat retreatment files are heat-treated NiTi instruments designed with a non-cutting tip, triangular cross-section with three equally spaced cutting edges and no radial lands, and progressive taper (larger taper coronally for bulk removal and decreasing taper apically for safer advancement), aiming to efficiently engage and remove gutta-percha while respecting canal anatomy.¹⁹

Compared to the ProTaper Universal Retreatment system and Neo Endo retreatment file, the Micro-Mega RETREAT files exhibit higher percentage of residual root canal filling material with the difference being statistically significant. Reason may be attributed to certain design-related limitations. The non-cutting tip and heat-treated NiTi alloy of the RETREAT system, while enhancing flexibility and safety in curved canals, may reduce penetration efficiency in dense or aged gutta-percha, often necessitating the use of solvents or prior coronal enlargement. Additionally, triangular cross-section without radial lands may offer reduced guidance within the canal, increasing the risk of canal deviation. The progressive taper design, although conservative in the apical region, may limit complete removal of obturating material from the apical third.¹⁹

The results obtained with the Retreat retreatment file system showed comparable efficacy in removing gutta-percha. The heat-treated NiTi alloy, triangular cross-section, and absence of radial lands in Retreat files allow effective engagement of the obturating material while minimizing excessive dentin removal. These design characteristics promote efficient cutting and coronal transportation of debris, thereby improving retreatment efficiency.

LIMITATION-

As this was an in-vitro investigation, the findings cannot be directly related to clinical situations.

The use of a single sealer restricts the generalizability of the results, as sealers differ in their adhesive and removal properties.

Additionally, the study was limited to straight premolar canals, whereas retreatment in clinical practice frequently involves curved and complex canal anatomies; therefore, the results may not be applicable to teeth with aberrant canals.

The short two-week interval between obturation and retreatment does not represent the variable time periods encountered clinically.

Consequently, further in-vitro and in-vivo studies are required to evaluate retreatment efficiency, preservation of original canal morphology, and the safety of rotary NiTi instruments in teeth with complex root canal anatomy under clinical conditions.

CONCLUSION-

Within the limitations of this study, none of the retreatment techniques were able to completely remove root canal filling material. Rotary retreatment systems demonstrated superior efficacy compared to manual techniques. Among the rotary systems evaluated, ProTaper Universal Retreatment files showed the least residual filling material, followed by Neo Endo Retreatment files, Retreat Retreatment file which may be attributed to their distinctive design features. In contrast, manual H-files exhibited the highest amount of remaining material, likely due to their limited flexibility.

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